

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

REVYMAE R. AVILA LPT

Teacher 1

Buraburon National High School

Division of Leyte

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17296249](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296249)

A Teacher's Lament

Our cries as teachers
Are not of the body,
But of the youth
The hope of the nation.

Blind to knowledge,
Mute in respect,
Deaf to discipline
These are their afflictions.

Awaken, youth!
What will become of the nation,
If you abandon
The path of virtue?